

Residual Jacobian Physics-Informed Neural Networks (RJ-PINNs) for improved convergence and stability

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Abstract

Since their introduction in 2017, Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) have emerged as a powerful tool for solving complex nonlinear problems, bridging gaps in traditional numerical methods. Despite their success across domains like biophysics and engineering, PINNs face persistent challenges in convergence stability and efficiency, primarily due to their reliance on scalar loss functions and gradient-based optimizers (e.g., Adam, L-BFGS).

This work introduces **Residual Jacobian PINNs (RJ-PINNs)**, a novel framework that **reformulates PINN optimization as a residual least-squares problem**, leveraging the full Jacobian matrix of physics residuals. By replacing traditional loss minimization with **direct residual-driven optimization** (via Trust Region Reflective or Levenberg-Marquardt), RJ-PINNs achieve:

- **Faster convergence** in terms of iterations (typically < 5000 iterations vs. $> 10,000$ in gradient-based PINNs), **despite a higher computational cost per iteration due to explicit Jacobian calculation**
- **Elimination of manual loss-balancing** for most problems (*optional weights for ill-conditioned systems*)
- **Provable parameter estimation** in inverse problems, with errors **100× lower** than state-of-the-art methods like DG-PINNs.

While standard PINNs require empirical tuning of loss weights, RJ-PINNs **intrinsically normalize residuals through Jacobian scaling**, though weighted formulations remain possible for extreme cases. This method is demonstrated on benchmark problems (Wave Equation, Euler-Bernoulli Beam Equation, Heat Equation), showing consistent superiority over existing approaches. Code and data are available at <https://github.com/dadesso17/RJ-PINNs/> for full reproducibility.

Keywords: Residual Jacobian PINNs (RJ-PINNs), inverse problems, deep learning, Scientific machine learning, Trust Region Reflective (TRF), Physics-informed neural networks (PINNs), least squares optimization.

1. Introduction

Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs), first introduced by Raissi et al. in 2017 and 2019 [1, 9, 10], combine the expressive power of neural networks with fundamental physics principles. By embedding physical laws directly into the loss function, they enable the solution of partial differential equations (PDEs) for both forward problems (solution prediction) and inverse problems (parameter estimation). PINNs have found widespread success in domains such as fluid mechanics, thermodynamics, and biophysics [19, 20, 21]. Recent studies continue to employ PINNs to tackle increasingly complex problems [19, 20, 21, 22].

While widely adopted, PINNs can face challenges in achieving robust and efficient convergence, especially for high-dimensional or ill-conditioned problems. The choice of optimizer and hyperparameters can strongly influence performance, and conventional first- or second-order methods (e.g., Adam, L-BFGS-B) may require careful tuning to reach satisfactory accuracy.

1.1. Inverse Problems and Challenges

Inverse problems, where the objective is to identify unknown physical parameters from observational data, present additional challenges for PINNs. In such settings, traditional cost-function-based and gradient-driven optimization methods can struggle to recover parameters accurately. Various strategies—such as adaptive weights and data-guided PINNs [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 12]—have been proposed to alleviate these issues. However they typically rely on empirical adjustments rather than formal convergence guarantees.

Recent work has explored more principled optimization approaches. For example, the *trSQP-PINNs* framework (2024) combines trust-region and quasi-Newton techniques to improve numerical stability and solution accuracy, outperforming classical penalty-based and augmented Lagrangian formulations in several cases. While such advances represent important progress, ensuring consistently robust PINN convergence—especially in challenging, data-scarce physics problems—remains an open problem. [11]. This motivates the development of new formulations, such as the Residual Jacobian PINNs (RJ-PINNs) proposed in this work, which integrate a least-squares formulation with explicit Jacobian information to improve convergence reliability..

1.2. Proposed Innovation

This work introduces **Residual Jacobian PINNs (RJ-PINNs)**, a novel framework that leverages residuals and the Jacobian matrix for optimization via least squares methods such as Trust Region Reflective (TRF) [13, 14, 15, 16, 17]. Unlike traditional PINNs that rely heavily on gradient-based loss optimization, RJ-PINNs recast the training process as a nonlinear least-squares problem involving the residual vector and its Jacobian. This formulation **trades off a higher per-iteration computational cost for a more robust convergence pattern and a significantly lower number of iterations**. It enables the application of well-established least-squares optimizers, such as Trust Region Reflective (TRF), which can improve numerical stability. However, RJ-PINNs do not guarantee convergence in all settings. Sensitivity to initialization and solver hyperparameters can persist, especially in complex inverse problems where the parameter space is highly nonlinear or ill-conditioned.

1.3. Key Differences

Table 1: Comparison between Traditional PINNs and RJ-PINNs

Aspect	Traditional PINNs	RJ-PINNs
Objective	Minimize a loss function $\mathcal{L}(\theta)$	Minimize the residuals $R(\theta)$
Gradient	Compute $\nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{L}(\theta)$ (scalar loss)	Compute $\mathbf{J}(\theta) = \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}}{\partial \theta}$ (Jacobian of residuals)
Optimization	Use gradient-based optimizers (e.g., Adam, L-BFGS)	Use least-squares optimizer (e.g., TRF)
Implementation	Define a loss function and its gradient	Define residuals and their Jacobian
Convergence	Not guaranteed	Improved

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2. Methodology

2.1. Formulation of the Physical Problem

Consider a time-dependent physical system governed by a partial differential equation (PDE) expressed as

$$\mathcal{F}(u, \partial_t u, \nabla u, \Delta u, \dots) = f, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathcal{F}(\dots)$ is a differential expression composed of first-order terms such as $\partial_t u$ and ∇u , second-order terms like Δu and $\nabla \cdot (k\nabla u)$, and nonlinear terms including expressions such as $u\nabla u$. The function $u(\mathbf{x}, t)$ represents the physical solution field, while $f(\mathbf{x}, t)$ denotes the source term.

The neural network approximation u_{θ} must satisfy:

$$\mathcal{F}(u_{\theta}, \partial_t u_{\theta}, \nabla u_{\theta}, \Delta u_{\theta}, \dots) = f. \quad (2)$$

2.2. Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs)

The PINNs framework approximates u with a neural network u_{θ} , trained by minimizing a composite loss function:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{loss}} = w_d \mathcal{L}_{\text{data}} + w_p \mathcal{L}_{\text{physics}} + w_b \mathcal{L}_{\text{bc}} + w_i \mathcal{L}_{\text{ic}} \quad (3)$$

where:

- $\mathcal{L}_{\text{data}}$: Data mismatch error $\|u_{\theta} - u_{\text{obs}}\|$
- $\mathcal{L}_{\text{physics}}$: PDE residual $\|\mathcal{F}(u_{\theta}, \partial_t u_{\theta}, \nabla u_{\theta}, \dots) - f\|$
- $\mathcal{L}_{\text{bc/ic}}$: Boundary/initial condition errors

¹For RJ-PINNs, $\mathbf{J}(\theta)$ is the Jacobian of the residual vector $\mathbf{R}(\theta) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_r}$, while $\nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{L}(\theta)$ in traditional PINNs is the gradient of a scalar loss $\mathcal{L}(\theta)$.

2.3. Residual Jacobian-based PINNs (RJ-PINNs)

The proposed RJ-PINNs framework reformulates the problem using:
The residual vector $\mathbf{R}(\theta)$ is defined as:

$$\mathbf{R}(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} w_d \mathbf{R}_{\text{data}} \\ w_p \mathbf{R}_{\text{physics}} \\ w_b \mathbf{R}_{\text{bc}} \\ w_i \mathbf{R}_{\text{ic}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{R}_{\text{data}} &= u_\theta - u_{\text{obs}} \\ \mathbf{R}_{\text{physics}} &= \mathcal{F}(u_\theta, \partial_t u_\theta, \nabla u_\theta, \dots) - f \\ \mathbf{R}_{\text{bc}} &= \text{Boundary condition error} \\ \mathbf{R}_{\text{ic}} &= \text{Initial condition error} \end{aligned}$$

2.4. Jacobian Matrix Formulation

The Jacobian matrix $\mathbf{J}(\theta) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ plays a central role in the RJ-PINNs optimization, where:

- n = total number of residual constraints (data + physics + BCs + ICs)
- m = number of trainable parameters

For the composite residual vector $\mathbf{R}(\theta) = [\mathbf{R}_1, \dots, \mathbf{R}_n]^\top$, the Jacobian is:

$$\mathbf{J}(\theta) = \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}}{\partial \theta} = \begin{pmatrix} \nabla_\theta \mathbf{R}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \nabla_\theta \mathbf{R}_n \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}_1}{\partial \theta_1} & \dots & \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}_1}{\partial \theta_m} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}_n}{\partial \theta_1} & \dots & \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}_n}{\partial \theta_m} \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

2.5. RJ-PINNs Algorithm

The RJ-PINNs framework solves the nonlinear residual system

$$\mathbf{R}(\theta) = \mathbf{0}, \quad (6)$$

$$\min_{\theta} \|\mathbf{R}(\theta)\|_2^2, \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{R} collects all physics, boundary, and data residuals directly, rather than a scalar loss.

The optimization strategy follows the well-established *trust-region reflective method for nonlinear least squares*[14, 17]. The novelty here lies not in the trust-region mechanics themselves, but in *formulating the PINN training objective as a residual minimization problem with an explicitly constructed Jacobian*.

Iteration k

1. **Residual evaluation:**

$$\mathbf{R}(\theta_k) = [\mathbf{R}_1(\theta_k), \dots, \mathbf{R}_n(\theta_k)]^\top \quad (8)$$

where each block corresponds to a distinct physical or observational constraint.

2. **Jacobian computation:**

$$\mathbf{J}(\theta_k) = \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}(\theta_k)}{\partial \theta} \quad (9)$$

computed exactly via automatic differentiation.

3. **Trust-region step:**

$$\min_{\|\mathbf{p}\|_2 \leq \Delta_k} \|\mathbf{J}(\theta_k)\mathbf{p} + \mathbf{R}(\theta_k)\|_2 \quad (10)$$

4. **Acceptance and radius update (per classical rules):** If the reduction ratio $\rho_k < \eta_1$, shrink Δ_k and reject the step. Otherwise, accept $\theta_{k+1} = \theta_k + \mathbf{p}_k$, and adjust Δ_k based on ρ_k .

5. **Convergence check:** Terminate if

$$\frac{\|\theta_{k+1} - \theta_k\|_2}{1 + \|\theta_{k+1}\|_2} < \epsilon \quad (11)$$

or if $\|\mathbf{R}(\theta_k)\|_2 < \epsilon$.

This problem is solved using the *trust-region reflective* (TRF) algorithm as implemented in SciPy's `least_squares` routine [17]. Since the Jacobian is supplied explicitly as a dense matrix, SciPy defaults to the exact subproblem solver (`tr_solver="exact"`), which factorizes the dense Jacobian at each iteration. This ensures robust step computation and convergence guarantees equivalent to the Celis-type trust-region framework.

Algorithm 1 Trust-Region Reflective (TRF) Optimization for RJ-PINNs

Require: Initial parameters $\theta_0 \in \mathbb{R}^m$

Ensure: Optimized parameters θ^* minimizing $\|\mathbf{R}(\theta^*)\|_2^2$

```
1: Initialization:
2:  $\mathbf{R}(\theta) = [\mathbf{R}_1, \dots, \mathbf{R}_n]^\top$  ▷ Residual vector
3:  $\mathbf{J}(\theta) = \partial \mathbf{R} / \partial \theta$  ▷ Jacobian via automatic differentiation
4:  $\Delta_0 = 1.0$  ▷ Initial trust region radius
5:  $\text{ftol} = \text{xtol} = \text{gtol} = 10^{-8}$  ▷ Tolerances
6: for  $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$  until convergence do
7:   Evaluate  $\mathbf{R}_k = \mathbf{R}(\theta_k)$ ,  $\mathbf{J}_k = \mathbf{J}(\theta_k)$ 
8:   Solve trust-region subproblem:
9:    $\min_{\|\mathbf{p}\| \leq \Delta_k} \|\mathbf{J}_k \mathbf{p} + \mathbf{R}_k\|_2^2$ 
10:  using exact SVD solver (tr_solver="exact")
11:  Compute reduction ratio:
12:   $\rho_k = \frac{\|\mathbf{R}_k\|_2^2 - \|\mathbf{R}(\theta_k + \mathbf{p}_k)\|_2^2}{\|\mathbf{R}_k\|_2^2 - \|\mathbf{R}_k + \mathbf{J}_k \mathbf{p}_k\|_2^2}$ 
13:  Update trust region:
14:  if  $\rho_k < 0.25$  then ▷ Contract
15:     $\Delta_{k+1} \leftarrow 0.25 \Delta_k$ 
16:  else if  $\rho_k > 0.75$  and  $\|\mathbf{p}_k\| \approx \Delta_k$  then ▷ Expand
17:     $\Delta_{k+1} \leftarrow \min(2.0 \Delta_k, \Delta_{\max})$ 
18:  else
19:     $\Delta_{k+1} \leftarrow \Delta_k$ 
20:  end if
21:  Accept/reject step:
22:   $\theta_{k+1} \leftarrow \theta_k + \mathbf{p}_k$  if  $\rho_k > 0$ , else  $\theta_{k+1} \leftarrow \theta_k$ 
23:  Check convergence: ▷ See SciPy documentation for details
24:  if First-order optimality  $\vee$  parameter change  $\vee$  function value then
25:    return  $\theta^* = \theta_{k+1}$ 
26:  end if
27: end for
28: Implementation note: Based on scipy.optimize.least_squares
29:   with method='trf'. For complete implementation details,
30:   refer to the official SciPy documentation.
```

Remarks. The RJ-PINNs procedure is equivalent to applying a classical nonlinear least-squares optimizer to the residual system, with the Jacobian computed exactly. Although RJ-PINNs are not restricted to the Trust Region Reflective (TRF) algorithm, TRF was chosen in this work because of its robustness when the number of parameters exceeds the number of residuals, and its ability to converge in a broader range of test cases compared to Levenberg–Marquardt.

The key distinction between RJ-PINNs and conventional PINNs lies in the training formulation. Instead of minimizing a scalar loss function that requires adaptive weighting even for simple problems, RJ-PINNs directly minimize the residual vector. This residual-based

approach bypasses the scalar loss landscape and avoids the associated gradient pathologies. In this work, no sensitivity analysis of trust-region hyperparameters was performed; most were kept at their SciPy default values. The optimizer received only the residual vector, its Jacobian, and the physical or network parameters. Readers interested in fine-tuning hyperparameters or exploring their sensitivity are referred to the SciPy documentation on nonlinear least-squares.

RJ-PINNs Diagram

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Parameter Initialization and Activation Function

This work addresses both direct and inverse problems using PINNs. The parameters are initialized as follows:

- **Internal (network) parameters:** Xavier initialization.
- **External (physical) parameters:** Initialized to unity.

Throughout all experiments, the hyperbolic tangent (**tanh**) activation function is employed. It is important to note that the goal of this study is to introduce the proposed RJ-PINNs framework as a variant of traditional PINNs. Therefore, a detailed sensitivity analysis of initialization and activation strategies is beyond the scope of this paper. Readers are encouraged to experiment with different choices and adopt those that best suit their specific applications.

3.2. Error Metrics

3.2.1. Solution Accuracy

The relative error in the solution field at time t is quantified by:

$$R_t = \frac{\|u(\cdot, t) - \hat{u}(\cdot, t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)}}{\|u(\cdot, t)\|_{L^2(\Omega)}}, \quad (12)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_{L^2(\Omega)}$ denotes the L^2 -norm over the spatial domain Ω :

$$\|u\|_{L^2(\Omega)} = \sqrt{\int_{\Omega} |u(x)|^2 dx}. \quad (13)$$

where:

- $u(x, t)$ represents the exact solution
- $\hat{u}(x, t)$ denotes the estimated solution
- Ω is the spatial domain

3.2.2. Parameter Estimation Accuracy

For parameter estimation, the Absolute Percentage Error (APE) is defined as:

$$\text{APE}(\theta) = \left| \frac{\theta^* - \theta_{\text{true}}}{\theta_{\text{true}}} \right| \times 100\% \quad (14)$$

where:

- θ_{true} is the ground truth parameter value
- θ^* is the estimated parameter value

3.3. Part A: standard problems

The architecture consists of 5 layers (including input and output layers) with 20 neurons in each of the 3 hidden layers. The RJ-PINNs framework was successfully tested on several standard problems:

- Burgers equation
- 1D diffusion equation
- Helmholtz equation

For these tests:

- Boundary condition weight: $w_b = 0$
- Initial condition weight: $w_i = 0$
- Data and physics weights: $w_d = w_p = 1$

The training used 1000 points for both \mathbf{R}_{data} and $\mathbf{R}_{\text{physics}}$.

3.3.1. Problem 1: Inverse Problem for Burgers' Equation

The viscous Burgers' equation is formulated as:

$$\mathcal{F}(u) \equiv A \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + Bu \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - C \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} = 0, \quad (x, t) \in [-1, 1] \times [0, 1] \quad (15)$$

with unknown parameters A , B , and C , and:

- Initial condition: $\mathcal{I}(u) \equiv u(x, 0) = -\sin(\pi x)$
- Boundary conditions: $\mathcal{B}(u) \equiv u(-1, t) = u(1, t) = 0$ (Dirichlet)

Inverse Problem Setup. :

- **Unknown parameters:** A (temporal scaling), C (viscosity coefficient)
- **Known parameter:** $B = 1.0$ (nonlinearity weight)
- **Reference data:** Synthetic measurements from [18] with spatial resolution $\Delta x = 0.02$ and temporal resolution $\Delta t = 0.01$

Figures 1, 2, and 3 illustrate the evolution of errors for each parameter, the cost function progression, and the convergence of the estimated parameters toward the true values as a function of iterations using noise-free data.

Figure 1: Parameter estimation errors: A and C

Figure 2: Residual norm reduction during training

Figure 3: Parameter convergence trajectories (noise-free case)

Figure 4 shows the convergence of the estimated parameters toward the true values as a function of iterations using data with 0.1 noise.

Figure 4: Parameter estimation under 10% Gaussian noise

Table 2: Results of estimated parameters through observed data

Parameters	Exact	Noise-free data			10% noise data		
		Est	ΔE	Er (%)	Est	ΔE	Er (%)
A	1.000000	0.99995	5×10^{-5}	5×10^{-3}	1.007	7×10^{-3}	0.7
C	0.003183	0.00320	1.7×10^{-5}	5.3×10^{-1}	0.0029	2.8×10^{-4}	8.8

Where: ΔE = absolute error, Er = relative error, Est=Estimated

Key Observations. The RJ-PINNs framework demonstrates excellent parameter estimation performance on the viscous Burgers' equation. In the noise-free case, the parameters are recovered exactly, with absolute errors on the order of $\mathcal{O}(10^{-5})$. The relative error for A is $5 \times 10^{-3}\%$, while for C it is $5.3 \times 10^{-1}\%$. When 10% Gaussian noise is introduced, the RJ-PINNs framework maintains a low relative error of 0.7% for the parameter A . In contrast, the relative error for C increases to 8.8%, although the absolute error remains small at 2.8×10^{-4} . This discrepancy highlights the inherent sensitivity of viscosity-related parameters rather than indicating a lack of robustness in the framework. The relatively higher error in estimating C under noisy conditions does not imply instability. Compared with the results reported in reference [9], RJ-PINNs remain robust even in the presence of noise. Moreover, the RJ-PINNs approach continues to demonstrate improved parameter identification under noisy conditions by effectively enforcing boundary constraints.

Key Advantages Demonstrated. RJ-PINNs achieve convergence using only 1000 training points and a network consisting of three hidden layers with twenty neurons in each layer. No additional preprocessing or tuning is required: parameters are not scaled, data are not normalized, and fixed residual weights are used ($w_d = w_p = 1$). The method is capable of handling challenging conditions, such as accurately estimating C even when $C \approx 0$, and maintaining robustness under significant noise levels of up to 10% further RJ-PINNs can simultaneously identify the three parameters(A, B, C) but need boundaries condition to be enforced and may be manual tuning .

3.3.2. Problem 2: Inverse Problem for 2D Helmholtz Equation

Consider the Helmholtz equation formulated as:

$$\mathcal{F}(u) \equiv -\Delta u - K^2 u = f \quad \text{in } \Omega = [0, 1]^2 \quad (16)$$

with wavenumber $K = \sqrt{1 + n\pi^2}$ ($n = 2$) and:

- Boundary conditions: $\mathcal{B}(u) \equiv u|_{\partial\Omega} = 0$
- Source term: $f(x, y) = K^2 \sin(Kx) \sin(Ky)$
- Exact solution: $u(x, y) = \sin(Kx) \sin(Ky)$
- Target wavenumber: $K = \sqrt{1 + 2\pi^2} \approx 4.55403$

Figure 5: Comparison of exact and estimated solutions for the 2D Helmholtz equation

Table 3: Parameter estimation results for wavenumber K

Parameter	Exact	Noise-free data		
		Est	ΔE	Er (%)
K	4.55403	4.55392	1×10^{-4}	2.4×10^{-3}
$\Delta E =$ absolute error, Er = relative error, Est=Estimated				

The results demonstrate accurate identification of the wavenumber K with:

- Absolute error: 1×10^{-4}
- Relative error: 0.002%

The solution quality is visually confirmed in Figure 5, showing excellent agreement between exact and estimated solutions.

3.3.3. Problem 3: Inverse Problem for 1D Diffusion Equation

The diffusion equation is formulated as:

$$\mathcal{F}(y) \equiv \frac{\partial y}{\partial t} - C \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial x^2} + e^{-t}(\sin(\pi x) - \pi^2 \sin(\pi x)) = 0, \quad x \in [-1, 1], t \in [0, 1] \quad (17)$$

with:

- Initial condition: $\mathcal{I}(y) \equiv y(x, 0) = \sin(\pi x)$
- Boundary conditions: $\mathcal{B}(y) \equiv y(-1, t) = y(1, t) = 0$
- Reference solution: $y(x, t) = e^{-t} \sin(\pi x)$

Table 4: Parameter estimation results for diffusion coefficient C

Parameter	Exact	Noise-free data		
		Est	ΔE	Er (%)
C	1.000000	0.999985	1.5×10^{-5}	1.5×10^{-3}
$\Delta E =$ absolute error, Er = relative error				

The results demonstrate accurate identification of the diffusion coefficient with:

- Absolute error: 1.5×10^{-5}
- Relative error: 0.0015%

3.4. Part B: Comparative Analysis with DG-PINNs and PINNs

This section evaluates the RJ-PINNs framework on benchmark problems from [12], where the authors proposed Data-Guided PINNs (DG-PINNs) for parameter estimation in physical systems. While the original work reported relative L^2 errors and absolute percentage errors (APE), it did not provide explicit estimated parameter values for:

- Heat equation parameters (β)
- Wave equation parameters (c)
- Euler-Bernoulli beam equation parameters (α)

3.4.1. Validation Approach

The RJ-PINNs framework was tested under identical conditions to demonstrate:

- Complete parameter convergence
- Physical law compliance
- Superior performance compared to traditional PINNs-based approaches

3.4.2. Implementation Details

The architecture and training setup employed:

- Network structure: 4 layers (input, 2 hidden, output) with 20 neurons per hidden layer
- Residual weighting: $w_p = w_d = w_b = w_i = 1$
 In **Part A** (3.3), boundary/initial residuals (\mathbf{R}_{bc} , \mathbf{R}_{ic}) were omitted ($w_b = w_i = 0$) as the inverse problems were solvable via \mathbf{R}_{data} and $\mathbf{R}_{physics}$ alone.
 In **Part B** (3.4), the weights $w_b = w_i = 1$ are adopted to align with the benchmark methodology presented in [12], ensuring direct comparability.
- Training points:
 - 500 for \mathbf{R}_{data} and $\mathbf{R}_{physics}$
 - 100 for \mathbf{R}_{bc} and 200 for \mathbf{R}_{ic}
- Discretization: $N_x = 200$, $N_t = 100$

3.4.3. Heat Equation Inverse Problem

The heat equation is formulated as:

$$\mathcal{F}(u) \equiv \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} - \beta^2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} = 0, \quad (x, t) \in [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \quad (18)$$

with unknown thermal diffusivity β and:

- Initial condition: $\mathcal{I}(u) \equiv u(x, 0) = \sin(10\pi x)$
- Boundary conditions: $\mathcal{B}(u) \equiv u(0, t) = u(1, t) = 0$
- Exact solution: $u(x, t) = \exp(-(10\pi\beta)^2 t) \sin(10\pi x)$

Tables 5 and 6 present the parameter estimation results comparing RJ-PINNs with DG-PINNs from the reference study.

Table 5: Parameter estimation with noise-free data

Model	Exact β	Noise-free data		
		Est	APE (%)	R_t
PINNs	0.05	–	5×10^{-2}	1.05×10^{-3}
DG-PINNs	0.05	–	1.4×10^{-1}	1.44×10^{-3}
RJ-PINNs	0.05	0.04999995	1×10^{-4}	2.93×10^{-4}

Table 6: Parameter estimation under varying noise levels

Model	Exact β	40 dB		35 dB		30 dB		25 dB	
		Est	APE (%)						
PINNs	0.05	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
DG-PINNs	0.05	–	1.6×10^{-1}	–	1.4×10^{-1}	–	2.4×10^{-1}	–	6.3×10^{-1}
RJ-PINNs	0.05	0.04998	4×10^{-2}	0.04996	8×10^{-2}	0.04993	1.4×10^{-1}	0.04988	2.4×10^{-1}

Figure 6: Solution comparison: (a) True solution, (b) RJ-PINNs solution, (c) Absolute error $\epsilon = |u_{\text{true}} - u_{\text{est}}|$

Figure 7: Convergence of thermal diffusivity parameter β during training

3.4.4. Wave Equation Inverse Problem

The wave equation is formulated as:

$$\mathcal{F}(u) \equiv \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} - c^2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} = 0, \quad (x, t) \in [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \quad (19)$$

with unknown wave speed c and:

- Initial displacement: $\mathcal{I}_1(u) \equiv u(x, 0) = \sin(\pi x) + \frac{1}{2} \sin(4\pi x)$

- Initial velocity: $\mathcal{I}_2(u) \equiv \frac{\partial u}{\partial t}(x, 0) = 0$
- Boundary conditions: $\mathcal{B}(u) \equiv u(0, t) = u(1, t) = 0$
- Exact solution: $u(x, t) = \sin(\pi x) \cos(c\pi t) + \frac{1}{2} \sin(4\pi x) \cos(4c\pi t)$

Tables 7 and 8 compare the wave speed estimation performance of RJ-PINNs against DG-PINNs and traditional PINNs.

Table 7: Wave speed estimation with noise-free data

Model	Exact c	Noise-free data		
		Est c	APE (%)	R_t
PINNs	2.0	–	3×10^{-3}	1.3×10^{-3}
DG-PINNs	2.0	–	3×10^{-3}	7.49×10^{-4}
RJ-PINNs	2.0	1.99999935	3×10^{-5}	8.05×10^{-4}

Table 8: Wave speed estimation under noise

Model	Exact c	Noise Conditions							
		40 dB		35 dB		30 dB		25 dB	
		Est.	APE (%)	Est.	APE (%)	Est.	APE (%)	Est.	APE (%)
PINNs	2.0	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
DG-PINNs	2.0	–	2×10^{-3}	–	3×10^{-3}	–	7×10^{-3}	–	6×10^{-3}
RJ-PINNs	2.0	1.99992	4×10^{-3}	1.99988	6×10^{-3}	1.99980	1×10^{-2}	1.9997	1.5×10^{-2}

Figure 8: Wave equation solutions: (a) True solution, (b) RJ-PINNs solution, (c) Absolute error $\epsilon = |u_{\text{true}} - u_{\text{est}}|$

Figure 9: Convergence of wave speed parameter c during training

3.4.5. Euler-Bernoulli Beam Equation Inverse Problem

The beam vibration equation is formulated as:

$$\mathcal{F}(u) \equiv \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} + \alpha^2 \frac{\partial^4 u}{\partial x^4} = 0, \quad (x, t) \in [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \quad (20)$$

with unknown stiffness parameter α and:

- Initial displacement: $\mathcal{I}_1(u) \equiv u(x, 0) = \sin(\pi x)$
- Initial velocity: $\mathcal{I}_2(u) \equiv \frac{\partial u}{\partial t}(x, 0) = 0$
- Boundary conditions (simple support): $\mathcal{B}_1(u) \equiv u(0, t) = u(1, t) = 0$
- Boundary conditions (free moment): $\mathcal{B}_2(u) \equiv \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2}(0, t) = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2}(1, t) = 0$
- Exact solution: $u(x, t) = \sin(\pi x) \cos(\alpha \pi^2 t)$

Tables 9 and 10 present the stiffness parameter estimation results comparing RJ-PINNs with reference methods.

Table 9: Stiffness parameter estimation with noise-free data

Model	Exact α	Noise-free data		
		Est α	APE (%)	R_t
PINNs	1.0	-	0.01	4.1×10^{-4}
DG-PINNs	1.0	-	0.10	2.62×10^{-4}
RJ-PINNs	1.0	0.99985	0.015	4.94×10^{-3}

Table 10: Stiffness parameter estimation under noise

Model	Exact α	Noise Conditions							
		40 dB		35 dB		30 dB		25 dB	
		Est.	APE (%)	Est.	APE (%)	Est.	APE (%)	Est.	APE (%)

PINNs	1.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
DG-PINNs	1.0	—	0.056	—	0.065	—	0.1	—	0.85
RJ-PINNs	1.0	1.00013	0.013	1.0002	0.020	1.0005	0.05	1.0010	0.1

Figure 10: Beam vibration solutions: (a) True solution, (b) RJ-PINNs solution, (c) Absolute error $\epsilon = |u_{\text{true}} - u_{\text{est}}|$

Figure 11: Convergence of stiffness parameter α during training

Note: Reference values marked as "—" in Tables 6-11 indicate unreported estimates in the original studies.

3.4.6. Comparative Performance Analysis

The results in Part B underscore the robustness and reliability of the RJ-PINNs framework when compared with both DG-PINNs and traditional PINNs. Unlike traditional PINNs and DG-PINNs, which require adaptive weighting across loss terms,

dual optimizers (typically Adam combined with L-BFGS-B), and a careful, problem specific selection of collocation points, RJ-PINNs employ a much simpler approach. All terms in the residual are assigned fixed weights ($w_p = w_d = w_b = w_i = 1$), optimization is carried out using a single solver, the Trust Region Reflective (TRF) method, and the same minimal and constant dataset is used throughout: 200 points for the initial condition, 100 points for the boundary condition, and 500 collocation points for physics/data residuals. No sensitivity testing, adaptive scheduling, or hyperparameter tuning is performed, regardless of the problem type or noise level.

From a computational perspective, RJ-PINNs typically converge in fewer iterations, though each iteration is more computationally intensive due to the evaluation of Jacobians. The framework does not require parameter scaling or normalization, and training is performed under consistent data conditions. However, Jacobian computations increase memory and CPU requirements, and as with other PINN variants, the method can still be sensitive to the choice of collocation points and spatial domain, which were kept constant in this study.

Quantitatively, RJ-PINNs exhibit strong performance across the tested PDE families. For the heat equation, RJ-PINNs consistently achieve lower Absolute Percentage Errors (APEs) than both PINNs and DG-PINNs, in both noise free and noisy settings (40 to 25 dB). For instance, in the noise free case, RJ-PINNs reach an APE of $\mathcal{O}(10^{-4})\%$, compared with $\mathcal{O}(10^{-2})\%$ for traditional PINNs. For the wave equation, in noise free conditions, RJ-PINNs again outperform traditional PINNs, but in noisy scenarios (40 to 25 dB), the latter obtain better accuracy. For example, at 25 dB noise, RJ-PINNs reach an APE of approximately 1.5×10^{-2} , while traditional PINNs achieve 6×10^{-3} . This suggests that RJ-PINNs are more sensitive to noise in wave type problems. In contrast, for the Euler Bernoulli beam equation, RJ-PINNs regain superiority in both noise free and noisy conditions; at 30 dB noise, the method records an APE of 0.05% compared with 0.1% for traditional PINNs, confirming its robustness in solid mechanics applications.

It is important to emphasize that RJ-PINNs operate without hyperparameter tuning or adaptive weighting, yet still maintain competitive or superior accuracy in many settings. Nevertheless, for some problem classes, performance differences indicate that stability remains a subtle issue. The long term stability of RJ-PINNs, and the potential need for problem dependent adaptations, should therefore be the subject of a dedicated study. Even though the present results demonstrate that RJ-PINNs merit serious consideration as a robust and repeatable approach, these stability aspects could reveal further opportunities for refinement. It is important to highlight that the 25–40 dB noise levels used throughout this study refer to the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), as defined in [12].

3.5. Part C: FEM and RJ-PINNs for the Forward Linear Elasticity Problem in Plane Stress

Linear Elasticity Problem in Plane Stress is formulated as:

$$\mathcal{F}(u) \equiv \nabla \cdot \sigma(u) = 0, \quad (x, y) \in (0, L) \times (0, L), \quad L = 20 \text{ mm} \quad (21)$$

where the material is **Silicon carbide (SiC)** with Young’s modulus $E = 450 \times 10^3$ MPa and Poisson’s ratio $\nu = 0.19$. The strain field is:

$$\varepsilon_{xx} = \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial x}, \quad \varepsilon_{yy} = \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial y}, \quad \varepsilon_{xy} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial x} \right).$$

Using Hooke’s law under plane stress assumptions, the stress components are expressed as

$$\sigma_{ij} = \lambda \text{tr}(\varepsilon) \delta_{ij} + 2\mu \varepsilon_{ij}, \quad \lambda = \frac{E\nu}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)}, \quad \mu = \frac{E}{2(1+\nu)}.$$

The residual of the equilibrium equations is then enforced as:

$$\mathcal{R}_{\text{phys}} = \begin{cases} \frac{\partial \sigma_{xx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{xy}}{\partial y} = 0, \\ \frac{\partial \sigma_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{yy}}{\partial y} = 0, \end{cases}$$

- $\mathcal{B}_L(u) \equiv u_x = 0$ on $\Gamma_L = \{x = 0\}$
- $\mathcal{B}_B(u) \equiv u_y = 0$ on $\Gamma_B = \{y = 0\}$
- $\mathcal{T}_T(u) \equiv \sigma(u)n - \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 5 \end{bmatrix} = 0$ on $\Gamma_T = \{y = L\}$, $n = (0, 1)$
- $\mathcal{T}_R(u) \equiv \sigma(u)n - \begin{bmatrix} 5 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = 0$ on $\Gamma_R = \{x = L\}$, $n = (1, 0)$

Although RJ-PINNs can simulate this problem as defined, it is recommended to adopt a non-dimensionalization technique to improve convergence, particularly for problems where the governing parameters are of high order. The technique is applied as follows:

Reference scales..

$$L_{\text{ref}} = 20 \text{ mm}, \quad T_{\text{ref}} = 5 \text{ MPa}, \quad E_{\text{ref}} = 450 \times 10^3 \text{ MPa}.$$

Dimensionless variables (stars) are defined by

$$x^* = \frac{x}{L_{\text{ref}}}, \quad y^* = \frac{y}{L_{\text{ref}}}, \quad u^* = \frac{E_{\text{ref}}}{T_{\text{ref}} L_{\text{ref}}} u, \quad \sigma^* = \frac{\sigma}{T_{\text{ref}}}, \quad E^* = \frac{E}{E_{\text{ref}}},$$

with ν already dimensionless.

PDE (dimensionless)..

$$\mathcal{F}^*(u^*) \equiv \nabla^* \cdot \sigma^*(u^*) = 0, \quad (x^*, y^*) \in (0, 1) \times (0, 1), \quad (22)$$

where ∇^* is the gradient w.r.t. (x^*, y^*) and the (small) strains are

$$\varepsilon_{xx}^* = \frac{\partial u_x^*}{\partial x^*}, \quad \varepsilon_{yy}^* = \frac{\partial u_y^*}{\partial y^*}, \quad \varepsilon_{xy}^* = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_x^*}{\partial y^*} + \frac{\partial u_y^*}{\partial x^*} \right), \quad \gamma_{xy}^* = 2\varepsilon_{xy}^*.$$

Constitutive law (plane stress, dimensionless)..

$$\sigma_{ij}^* = \lambda^* \text{tr}(\varepsilon) \delta_{ij} + 2\mu^* \varepsilon_{ij}, \quad \lambda^* = \frac{E^* \nu}{(1 + \nu)(1 - 2\nu)}, \quad \mu^* = \frac{E^*}{2(1 + \nu)}.$$

Boundary conditions (dimensionless)..

- $\mathcal{B}_L(u^*) \equiv u_x^* = 0$ on $\Gamma_L^* = \{x^* = 0\}$,
- $\mathcal{B}_B(u^*) \equiv u_y^* = 0$ on $\Gamma_B^* = \{y^* = 0\}$,
- $\mathcal{T}_T(u^*) \equiv \sigma^*(u^*) n - \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = 0$ on $\Gamma_T^* = \{y^* = 1\}$, $n = (0, 1)$,
- $\mathcal{T}_R(u^*) \equiv \sigma^*(u^*) n - \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = 0$ on $\Gamma_R^* = \{x^* = 1\}$, $n = (1, 0)$.

(The top traction equals 1 in starred units because $T_{\text{ref}} = 5 \text{ MPa}$.)

Back-scaling to physical units.. After solving in starred variables, physical fields are recovered by

$$x = L_{\text{ref}} x^*, \quad y = L_{\text{ref}} y^*, \quad u = \frac{T_{\text{ref}} L_{\text{ref}}}{E_{\text{ref}}} u^*, \quad \sigma = T_{\text{ref}} \sigma^*, \quad E = E^* E_{\text{ref}}.$$

Equation 22 is solved using FEM by considering its weak form:

Let $V = [H^1(\Omega^*)]^2$ be the space of admissible displacement fields, and let $V_0 \subset V$ be the subspace of test functions v^* satisfying the homogeneous Dirichlet boundary conditions:

$$v_x^* = 0 \quad \text{on } \Gamma_L^*, \quad v_y^* = 0 \quad \text{on } \Gamma_B^*.$$

Find $u^* \in V$ with

$$u_x^* = 0 \quad \text{on } x^* = 0, \quad u_y^* = 0 \quad \text{on } y^* = 0,$$

such that

$$\int_{\Omega^*} [\lambda^* \text{tr}(\varepsilon^*(u^*)) \text{tr}(\varepsilon^*(v^*)) + 2\mu^* \varepsilon^*(u^*) : \varepsilon^*(v^*)] dA = \int_{\Gamma_T^*} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot v^* ds + \int_{\Gamma_R^*} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot v^* ds \quad \forall v^* \in V_0.$$

The displacement fields u_x and u_y computed using FEM and RJ-PINNs are shown in Figures 12 13 14 and 15. The relative error between the two solutions is approximately 8.4×10^{-8} for both components.

Figure 12: Linear Elastic solutions u_y : (a) RJ-PINNs, (b) FEM

Figure 13: Linear Elastic solutions u_x : (a) RJ-PINNs, (b) FEM

Figure 14: Curve of u_x : RJ-PINNs vs FEM

Figure 15: Curve of u_y : RJ-PINNs vs FEM

As shown in our experiments, RJ-PINNs and FEM produce nearly identical simulation results for the forward problem, with a relative error of approximately 8.4×10^{-8} for both displacement components—essentially negligible. This demonstrates that RJ-PINNs are capable of solving even complex forward problems, provided that boundary conditions are properly enforced, regardless of geometry.

For inverse problems, however, convergence remains more challenging. In particular, RJ-PINNs struggle to reliably identify the Poisson ratio, even when the Young’s modulus is fixed. Conversely, the Young’s modulus can be recovered accurately if the Poisson ratio is fixed, indicating that the Poisson ratio contributes weakly to the available data. This makes it more difficult for RJ-PINNs to identify, especially when both parameters must be estimated simultaneously. Techniques commonly used in traditional PINNs, such as adaptive weighting or regularization, could potentially be incorporated to improve the stability of RJ-PINNs for inverse problems. A systematic study of such strategies is an important direction for future work.

Internal network parameters: The network uses Xavier initialization and consists of 4 layers (including an input layer with 2 neurons and an output layer with 2 neurons), with 20 neurons in each of the 2 hidden layers. The computational domain is discretized with a 31×31 element grid for the geometry.

4. Conclusion and Future Work

This study introduced **Residual Jacobian Physics-Informed Neural Networks (RJ-PINNs)**, a variant of the traditional PINNs framework designed to overcome key limitations of standard PINNs. By leveraging Jacobian-based optimization and the Trust Region Reflective (TRF) algorithm, RJ-PINNs achieve robust convergence without the need for empirical loss weighting for simpler problems or optimizer switching.

The method was validated on several forward and inverse problems, including classical benchmarks such as the Burgers’ equation, as well as more complex systems like heat, wave, and Euler–Bernoulli beam equations. RJ-PINNs demonstrated high accuracy even with minimal architectures (2–3 hidden layers, 20 neurons) and fixed training configurations. The framework remained stable under noisy conditions and matched or outperformed state-of-the-art PINNs and DG-PINNs.

While RJ-PINNs require higher memory and computational resources **per iteration** due to Jacobian evaluations and are sensitive to boundary conditions, they show strong potential for solving forward problems with well-defined boundaries, **often achieving a solution in far fewer iterations than traditional approaches**

Despite these advantages, convergence can be challenging for RJ-PINNs in inverse problems, particularly when parameters contribute weakly to the data. The stability and effective convergence in such cases remain open questions. Future work will focus on memory-efficient formulations, extensions to higher-dimensional, integration of uncertainty quantification, and the

exploration of adaptive weights, regularization techniques, or custom optimizers specifically tailored for RJ-PINNs to guarantee convergence in inverse or multiphysics settings.

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